

Cultic Practice at Khirbet Qeiyafa

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Khirbet Qeiyafa (ancient name unknown) is a fortified site overlooking the Elah Valley in hilly Shephelah region of the modern State of Israel. The site's main period of occupation was at the very beginning of the local Iron Age IIA, placed with the aid of radiocarbon dates c. 1020-980 BCE. There is some evidence for earlier occupation in the Middle Bronze Age and also limited occupation during the Hellenistic and Byzantine periods. On the basis of its geographical location, the site was most likely affiliated with the tribe of Judah and an early Israelite kingdom based on the highlands to the east, guarding one route that could be used by the Philistines to invade. N.B., the political history and archaeology of this period is extensively debated, and a social or political affiliation of the site is likewise a complex issue. The site's Iron Age IIA occupants appear to have rapidly abandoned the site and left much of what they had there behind, hence the site's material culture and extensively preserved. This includes spaces and objects that have been associated by the excavators with cultic activities, hence the site's relevance to research on religion in the southern Levant during the Iron Age. The primary loci of cultic activities were three separate spaces spread throughout the site that appear to have been used (exclusively or not) for cult, interpreted as such by the excavators on the basis of fixed and portable finds. Room G of Building C3 contained a stone bench, the opening of a drain apparently for liquids, a limestone basin, two stone-built installations of unclear purpose, two standing stones and a nearby flat stone interpreted as an offering table, a worked basalt altar of portable size, and a libation vessel with two rounded cups set on a tall base. In Courtyard E of Building C10 contained a basin above a drain, half of a basalt altar and fragments of a fenestrated ceramic stand. The adjacent Room F contained a unique type of cup-and-saucer vessel (much larger than any other excavated example from any site), while the adjacent Room G contained a bench and drain, a square stone platform (not fully preserved) and portable models, one stone and one ceramic, that appear to show the entrance of a temple. Fragments of both another ceramic model and a large cup-and-saucer vessel were found in other rooms of this building. Room A of Building D100 contained another twin-cup libation vessel, and one standing stone, as well as another possible standing stone, were found in adjacent rooms. A standing stone and bronze cup may also indicate a cultic space in the plaza of the site's southern gate complex. Other objects found throughout the site's Iron Age occupation, including an anthropomorphic figurine head, zoomorphic vessels, and chalices could be related to cultic activity.

Date Range: 1020 BCE - 980 BCE

Region: Khirbet Qeiyafa

Region tags: Israel

Khirbet Qeiyafa, located on a ridge overlooking the Elah Valley, Israel

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

The society in which the religious place is located is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Most likely the site belongs to a polity that can be defined as patrimonial in governance and kinship-based, but this is more certain if Khirbet Qeiyafa does indeed belong to an Israelite/Judahite polity (i.e. the biblical kingdoms(s) of the same name) located predominantly in the highlands to the east of the site. If it belongs to a local polity in its immediate surroundings in the Shephelah (one not clearly referred to in any source however), such a polity would likely have been much the same.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Field doesn't know

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Council of elders

– King or emperor

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Notes: Likely any one of, or a combination of, the above, but more than this is difficult to say.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Notes: N.B. the elevation relates to the strategic position of the site overall, rather than just the cultic spaces.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Field doesn't know

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are very few settlement sites of the same period as Khirbet Qeiyafa's occupation in the earliest phase of the Iron Age IIA in the region of the Shephelah, but it is likely that many mobile pastoralists who have left little archaeological trace did occupy the region and even make up the majority of its occupation in this period.

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1

– Source 2

– Source 3

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name

- ↳ Years of excavation:
 - Year range

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL
- Source 1 Description

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Yes

Notes: The features are all included within/associated with the structures, that is the various spaces interpreted as cultic.

- ↳ A single structure
 - No

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - No

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes
- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - No
- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship
 - ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

- ↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
 - Yes

Notes: The spaces that appear dedicated to cult are integrated within larger architectural units that form a single construction phase the rings the site, which includes the site's casemate defensive wall.

- ↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
 - No

- ↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
 - No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s).

Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Field doesn't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features of the iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Features of the portable models that appear to represent temples/shrines, the head of a figurine, and zoomorphic vessels (if the later are indeed cultic) could be taken as iconographic, but this needs more research.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Supernatural Beings

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is a supreme high god present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:
– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:
– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:
– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:
– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):
– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:
– Field doesn't know

Is supernatural monitoring present:
– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:
Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.
– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - No
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: David Ussishkin has proposed that the entire site was used for pilgrimage, see his article "The Function of the Iron Age Site of Khirbet Qeiyafa", *Israel Exploration Journal* 72:1 (2022), pp. 49-65. However, this explanation has not met with acceptance, and both overlooks many elements of the site's archaeology and raises more problems than it solves.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The excavators suggest that the concentration of six cooking installations in the large Building C10 relates to feasting activities. While they correctly point out that this is a much larger number of such installations than was found in any other single building at the site, the link with feasting remains one possible interpretation; for instance, it could indicate the number of individuals cooking for their own purposes living in the one building.

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Two inscriptions on pottery were found in the excavations; other writing on perishable media used in the Iron Age Levant (papyrus or parchment) could have been present, but have not survived.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely the references in the Hebrew Bible relevant to cultic practice at the site were originally oral.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Several elements of the site's cultic activity have references, or possible references, in the Hebrew Bible. This includes standing stones (Hebrew "Masseboth") and libation (Hebrew "nesekh") are referenced in the Hebrew Bible. The excavators interpreted the square stone platform in Building C10 as a biblical "bamah", usually translated as "high place". Altars, (Hebrew "mizbeach") also appear, though it is not clear if they might refer to the portable type found at Khirbet Qeiyafa. The excavators have also noted the possibility that the term "tavniyt heykhal" which appears in Psalm 144:12 may refer to a "temple model" and thus to the ceramic and stone models found at the site, but this is uncertain.

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– No

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Religious Specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It may be that any priests present (if so) also lived in the buildings where the cultic spaces were also located.

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Field doesn't know

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although not provable, it is likely that religious specialists (i.e. priests) were present among the population of the site at the time of its abandonment, given the concentration of cultic activities present.

Bureaucracy

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is possible, but again depends on both one's interpretation of the two inscriptions found at the site, and the large number of thumb impressions on the handles of the large corpus of storage jars found at the site. This subject requires further study.

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Whether or not "bureaucracy" (really administration more generally) is present depends on the interpretation of two inscriptions found at the site, neither of which are completely preserved and thus easy to reconstruct and interpret. Based on suggestions for their reconstruction and interpretation, both could relate to administration.

Bibliography

General References

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